

Location

Berlin, Germany

Innovation

Parametric BIM Automation tool
for Circular Economy

Partners

Technische Universität Berlin
BIM

DATA TYPES, TOOLS, REPOSITORIES, URLS

Data Types

- › BIM models (Revit files).
- › Marketplace databases of reclaimed windows in CSV format
- › Output files (e.g., CO₂ savings, material reuse rates) in CSV format.

Tools

- › Autodesk Revit (BIM modeling).
- › Dynamo (parametric automation).
- › Python (for data processing and matching logic).

SUMMARY OF SCOPE AND GOALS

The Kathreiner Haus project develops a Dynamo for Revit tool to automatically integrate reclaimed building components into BIM designs. This innovation drastically cuts material waste, and aligns with the Reincarnate mission to create closed-loop material cycles.

KEY PERFORMANCE INDICATORS

Quantitative Indicators

- › Success rate of matching reclaimed windows to BIM models.
- › Processing efficiency of the tool (time required for matching and integration).

Qualitative Indicators

- › Ease of use and user adoption among architects and engineers.
- › Stakeholder feedback on the tool's effectiveness in supporting circular practices in the design and procurement phase.
- › Potential for scalability to other building components (e.g., doors, structural elements).

IMPACT

MEDIUM

Techno-Economic
Impact

MEDIUM

Societal Impact

LOW

Scientific Impact

IMAGES

CONTACTS

Name

Jorg Theunissen

Organisation

Technische Universität Berlin

Email

j.theunissen@campus.tu-berlin.de